

Exploring Fragmentation in Emerging Fields of Research

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ABSTRACT

Thematic fragmentation within emerging fields can be a sign of positive diversity and dynamic heterogeneity, or a threat to scientific progress and collaboration. Especially a low self-awareness of the field may be crucial, as it could relate to thematic fragments with low exchange of knowledge. We address this issue by analyzing the effects of two indicators of fragmentation, self-referentiality and modularity in the citation network, on productivity and collaboration in the research field. Using the emerging field of translational psychotherapy as an example, we apply predictive modeling and examine a time span of 40 years (1982-2021). Results show that normalized self-referentiality (the number of direct citations divided by the number of possible citations within the research field) is positively related to the publication volume over time. In conclusion, the analysis of direct citations between thematic fragments in the research field seems promising for distinguishing between malignant disintegration and benign forms of fragmentation.

Keywords: bibliometrics; fragmentation; citation analysis; self-referentiality; network analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Emerging fields often experience thematic fragmentation, which poses challenges to scientific progress and interdisciplinary collaboration (Baliotti et al., 2015). The self-awareness of a research field is reflected in its actors' acknowledgment of the body of work produced within the field through reciprocal citations. This referencing practice signifies an active dialogue and a conscious engagement with the field's evolving knowledge. A lack of self-awareness, fueled by impeded findability of relevant studies, can lead to reduced collaboration and unfamiliarity with approaches already discussed in the literature. Such "reinvention of the wheel" clearly slows down scientific progress.

An example of an emerging field is translational psychotherapy. Translational research aims at translating findings from basic science (e.g., neuroscience) to applied settings (e.g. treatment). Unlike medical translational research, psychological translational research is still in its early stage (Ehring et al., 2022), and like many emerging fields, it is referred to by a variety of terms. For instance, "bench to bedside", "process-based", or "research utilization" may (or may not) point to similar translational efforts. Similarly, in a journal special issue entitled "Translating Basic Science into Clinical Practice" (Stice & Jansen, 2018), only five out of eleven articles, including the editorial, use the term "translation" (or its grammatical variants) in the title or abstract. This heterogeneity in terminology might be an indication of isolated fragments of research: Low self-awareness and exchange may hamper the development of common terminology, which ultimately impedes findability of respective studies.

While fragmentation can be a positive sign of specialization and dynamic heterogeneity, it can also hinder the development of coherent knowledge frameworks. This study aims to explore the role of self-referentiality, the extent to which researchers within a field refer to one another (as exemplified by Levy et al.; 2020), and citation clustering patterns within the scholarly literature of the field. In doing so, we seek to understand the circumstances in which fragmentation is a productive specialization or a threat to scientific progress and collaboration.

METHOD

Data

Our dataset comprised 682 translational psychotherapy research papers (with publication years ranging from 1982 to 2022), identified in a previous study (Bittermann et al., 2023), where bibliographic coupling (Kessler, 1963) indicated thematic clusters in the research field. For the current study, we excluded papers published in 2022, as this was the time of data collection and hence this year is not complete.

Indicators

Self-referentiality (SR) was calculated on a yearly basis as suggested by Levy et al. (2020): Inter-document citation rates (intracluster direct citations) in terms of number of links divided by number of documents. However, the

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maximum value of SR is dependent on the number of publications. For instance, for a total of three publications, the maximum SR is 1 (all three connections divided by three papers). For four publications, the maximum SR is 1.5 (six combinations divided by four papers), and so on. To increase interpretability, we normalized SR by dividing the observed SR by the maximum SR, which is equal to

$$SR_{normalized} = \frac{\text{observed self-referentiality}}{\text{maximum self-referentiality}} = \frac{\text{observed number of direct citations}}{\text{maximum number of direct citations}}$$

As for the second approach to citation fragmentation, we measured the modularity of the citation network (Shwed & Bearman, 2010). Specifically, we detected communities based on the Leiden algorithm (Traag et al., 2019) and determined the network modularity Q (i.e., division into subnetworks with many connections within these “modules” and few between them). A modularity value nearing 1 suggests a substantial presence of distinct communities.

Regarding outcome variables, productivity was operationalized as the number of publications per year. For collaborations, we used the annual average number of unique affiliations per publication.

ANALYTICAL PROCEDURE

First, we examined the pairwise correlations between all variables using Kendall’s tau. Next, we performed standard linear regression of $SR_{normalized}$ and Q on productivity (and collaborations, respectively) to check for multicollinearity and autoregression. Since the number of publications per year in our dataset followed a Poisson distribution, we applied a generalized linear model with lag 1 to take account for autocorrelated residuals. For collaborations, a standard linear model was used. To ensure the inferential robustness of the results, bootstrapping with 10,000 samples was utilized to calculate confidence intervals.

RESULTS

The mean number of publications across the years was 16.55 (SD = 22.37). Publications were authored on average by 1.42 different institutes (SD = 0.88). Citation network modularity Q (M = .27, SD = .28) was highly correlated (tau = .717, $z = 6.05$, $p < .001$) with the time variable (years). Hence, Q was excluded from the predictive models. $SR_{normalized}$ (M = 0.73, SD = 0.67) was a significant predictor for the number of publications over time ($b = 0.68$, 95% CI = [0.29, 0.91]). For collaboration, however, $SR_{normalized}$ showed no significant effect. A qualitative inspection of time segments in our dataset that exhibit relatively high $SR_{normalized}$ revealed that they were characterized by increased publication output as measured by the mean number of publications and an upward trend compared to segments with low $SR_{normalized}$.

DISCUSSION

In this study, the overall goal was to probe whether these proxies of self-awareness of the field are related to meaningful outcomes. In summary, the results show that the extent to which a field cites studies from the same field, was positively related to publication output. Whether this effect of self-referentiality on productivity can also be observed for thematic fragmentation, i.e., the role of direct citations between thematic fragments, is yet to be analyzed. One way to address this could be to first identify thematic fragments for different time periods, e.g. via bibliographic coupling. Next, direct citations between the fragments are used to quantify the between-fragment-awareness (in terms of citations). In the case of translational psychotherapy, this is of particular interest, as translational psychotherapy aims to translate findings from psychological basic sciences (such as social psychology or personality psychology; all distinct subfields of psychology) into therapeutic interventions (the subfield of clinical psychology and psychotherapy).

This exploration of fragmentation in emerging fields has several limitations. First, we focused on productivity as measured by publication output, and collaboration in terms of unique affiliations per publications. The role of a field’s self-awareness on the impact or perception of its published research (citations, altmetrics) may be of interest, assuming that increased information exchange can lead to higher quality research (Franceschet & Costantini, 2010). Collaboration could also be expressed by interdisciplinarity or across thematic subfields. Second, we used translational psychotherapy as an example, and whether the findings apply to other emerging fields remains to be explored. Third, the general interpretation of (normalized) self-referentiality is an open question, as no field will show a theoretical maximum of 100% (i.e., all papers of a field cite all others of the field).

As research evolves at a rapid pace and the volume of literature continues to grow (Bornmann et al., 2021), the risk of fragmentation may become more pronounced. The complexity and interconnectedness of interdisciplinary research requires a coherent framework and clear terminology to effectively navigate the vast landscape of scientific publications. In conclusion, analyzing the self-awareness of a research field can indeed be a promising approach for evaluating thematic fragmentation as a productive specialization or undermining of scientific progress. Further research is needed to shed light on this issue.

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